

28 **1. Introduction**

29 Lower back pain (LBP) is a common health condition that affects almost everyone at some
30 point in their lives, often leading to job incapacity and high treatment costs, which can result in
31 severe socioeconomic issues [1; 2]. Unfortunately, the cause of LBP is often unidentified or
32 misdiagnosed, leading to a prolonged treatment process. However, recent research suggests that
33 the thoracolumbar fascia (TLF) may be a potential cause of non-specific LBP due to its rich
34 innervation and function within the vertebrate body [3; 4; 5].

35

36 The TLF is a type of connective tissue composed of layers of pearly-white fibrous sheets. Its
37 purpose is to provide a broad attachment area for muscles, and isolate underlying muscles from
38 surrounding muscles or adipose tissue. Spanning the length of the back, the TLF consists of
39 two or three layers of collagen fibers separated by loose connective tissues [6; 7]. These tissues
40 contain fasciocytes, specialized cells responsible for producing hyaluronic acid (HA), which
41 lubricates the fascia [8]. This lubrication is crucial as it enables the different layers of the TLF
42 to glide over each other smoothly, facilitating free movement. The pathological changes of the
43 fascial tissue, such as fibrosis and densification, can lead to increased friction between the
44 layers, which may be a factor in the development of LBP [9; 10]. Therefore, injecting
45 a viscosupplement therapy into the fascia layers (as shown in Fig. 1) could potentially provide
46 relief for LBP. To precisely define the friction-reducing properties of viscosupplements, it is
47 necessary to investigate the effects of HA as a native lubricant on fascial friction.

48

49

50 *Fig. 1 Left side – Injection treatment of fascia by HA-based viscosupplement between to layers of pathological deep fascia.*
 51 *Right side – Situation between layers of deep fascia after viscosupplementation therapy. Created by Biorender.com.*

52

53 While there are numerous biotribological models available to study friction in the eye [11], skin
 54 [12; 13], or mouth [14; 15; 16], there is currently no model of fascia layers to study different
 55 conditions that influence friction in such an important organ that may be causing pain.
 56 As a result, this paper aims to develop a fascia model that can simulate real fascia and study
 57 friction in both healthy and afflicted tissue. By creating such a model, we hope to gain a better
 58 understanding of the role of the fascia in LBP and potentially improve treatment options for
 59 this common and debilitating condition. In a previous study [17], a preliminary model of fascia
 60 was created using polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) as an elastomer with low elastic moduli.
 61 However, this model was found to be unsuitable for mimicking fascia because of high stiffness
 62 of material pair and non-realistic point contact. Consequently, efforts are currently focused on
 63 the search for a more authentic elastomer to develop a tribological fascia model. The
 64 development of artificial models based on technical materials is usually based on friction
 65 comparisons. Of course, friction is affected by the model configuration and conditions, so it is
 66 a good idea to base the model on the standard conditions (configurations) used for the
 67 application - i.e. two muscles divided by fascia layers. To achieve this objective, more
 68 compliant technical materials are being utilized, and a comparison is being made between their
 69 coefficient of friction (COF) and that of real fascia. Initially, rabbit TLF was considered as the
 70 most authentic model; nevertheless, employing biological tissue like rabbit fascia can be

71 inconvenient due to the necessity for dissection, transportation, and time-sensitive testing to
72 prevent tissue decay. Moreover, the mechanical properties of fascia undergo changes when
73 frozen, which adds to the difficulties involved in working with it. For more reason, see the
74 Limitations. Therefore, the search is ongoing for a technical material that can function as a
75 dependable fascia tribological model.

76

77 Previous studies by Bongaerts et al. [18] found that an increase in material roughness led to a
78 decrease in COF in the boundary lubrication regime, and the viscosity of the Newtonian
79 lubricant decreased friction in rougher contacts. Additionally, the contact angle of the plate-
80 lubricant interaction was found to be related to friction, with a lower contact angle leading to a
81 lower COF. Sadowski et al. [19] investigated the influence of substrate configuration and
82 viscoelasticity on friction using a PDMS-PDMS configuration and found that hysteresis losses
83 contributed significantly to friction. Selway et al. [20] studied the effects of fluid viscosity and
84 wetting on viscoelastic lubrication and found that rough contacts produced higher viscoelastic
85 hysteresis, increasing friction. The wettability of elastomers was also studied by Schneemilch
86 et al. [21] and Hillborg et al. [22] before and after surface oxidization. Tribological studies on
87 compliant planes with solid pins have been conducted by several other researchers.
88 Schallamach [23] discovered instability waves in sliding compliant contacts, leading to fatigue
89 fractures and wear, with the frequency and number of waves dependent on the elastic modulus
90 of the elastomer. De Vicente et al. [24] studied rolling and sliding friction in compliant
91 tribopairs and found that sliding friction was strongly dependent on the SRR in the EHL regime,
92 but had no effect in the boundary and mixed regimes, while rolling friction was independent of
93 SRR. Myant et al. [25] found that reducing elastic moduli leads to a drop in friction, and Xu et
94 al. [26] investigated the interfacial deformation of compliant contacts under the influence of

95 traction and normal force through numerical simulation, finding that the material deformed
96 unsymmetrically, and the cavity served as a lubricant reservoir.

97 The findings of these studies are important in the development of a tribological fascia model
98 that accurately represents compliant contacts involving biological samples. Understanding the
99 effects of material roughness, viscosity, wetting, and elastic moduli on friction can aid in
100 finding the technical material that mimics fascia more authentically. The tribology of compliant
101 contacts is well-researched and relevant to our study on the friction of fascia. The aim of this
102 study is to develop a tribological model of fascia through tribological modeling and material
103 substitution and study friction in these models. Thus, the model could be used to investigate
104 viscosupplement treatment, which aims to reduce pain by decreasing friction in the fascia
105 through the use of HA solution in the later stage of our investigation. This paper builds on a
106 previous study with a basic PDMS model [17] and presents an advanced tribological fascia
107 model with sheets to better mimic the real contact between layers of tissue.

108

109 **2. Materials and methods**

110 *2.1. Experimental apparatus and setup*

111 Determination of the frictional properties of the model and HA lubricants was performed
112 on the tribometer Bruker UMT TriboLab (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA). Sliding tests were
113 conducted in pin-on-plate configuration. The pin was stationary, holding the normal force
114 of 2 N. Unfortunately, no biomechanical study examined forces between fascia and muscle or
115 fascia layers. Nevertheless, the planned viscosupplement is meant to be utilized in conjunction
116 with manual therapy. According to a study by Albert et al. [27] mean hand force measured for
117 different massage techniques was 8.1 ± 2.7 N. The human hand presents a larger contact surface
118 during massage, and also, some of the load will be lost in the skin and fat, and the actual load
119 on the fascia may therefore be less. Plasqui et al. [28] demonstrated that the frequency range of
120 motion of daily activities was between 0.3 and 3.5 Hz. Therefore, the plate performed a linear

121 reciprocal movement with a frequency of 1 Hz (avg. velocity $24 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ as can be seen in Fig.
 122 2. The influence of motion speed was examined in our previous study [17]. Each step of the
 123 experiment with a 12 mm stroke was repeated 3 times separately on the new path and lasted
 124 300 s. The length of the path of 12 mm was determined by the study [5]. The range of fascia
 125 movement in this study was in men/women without pain $16.90 \pm 1.89/16.89 \pm 1.55 \text{ mm}$, with
 126 pain $9.74 \pm 0.86/16.28 \pm 1.92 \text{ mm}$. The scheme of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2.

127

128

129 *Fig. 2 a) scheme of experimental apparatus, b) velocity profile of bottom module for 1 Hz frequency and 12 mm path shown*
 130 *by the position of the LVDT sensor over time.*

131

132 For the model development and experiments, a holder and a pin were designed. The pot
 133 consisted of internal and external parts, where one is inserted into the other. The internal pot
 134 is used to insert a plate representing a muscle. The maximum possible size of the plate
 135 is 70x30 mm. The external pot was used to mount the tribometer platform and, at the same time,
 136 to heat the entire jig assembly. Heating is ensured by heating cartridges which maintain
 137 a temperature of $37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. There are studs on the external pot, on which holders for the models
 138 or real fasciae are inserted. One holder is static and the other is movable. Both holders are
 139 tightened with wing nuts. In the case of a movable holder, its position is also secured by double-
 140 head screws. First, the fascia is held in place by a static holder, then it is pre-tensioned with
 141 a movable holder, which is then secured. This design allows for easy replacement of fascia
 142 or tested lubricants.

143

144 The real fascia contact approaches the plate-on-plate configuration as friction arises between
145 the tissue layers. Although plate-on-plate configuration was omitted for undesirable edge
146 effects. To approach this situation and to study the influence of tribopair geometry, the original
147 pin of 8.6 mm radius was supplemented by two sizes of cylindrical surface radii – 30 mm (R30)
148 and 50 mm (R50), which allows for the use of base material thicknesses of 3.5 mm. The
149 construction of the pin consisted of the pin itself and two holders. The pin is formed by a
150 cylindrical tip that is in contact with the bath during the experiments. The muscle model is glued
151 to the cylindrical contact surface. The fascia is fastened in one holder and then manually
152 prestressed over the cylindrical surface and fastened with the other holder. The pin prepared in
153 this way is inserted and secured in the upper part of the tribometer.

154

155 2.2. *Materials*

156 Models representing muscles and fascia are made up of PDMS, PU Gels, PVA hydrogel, and
157 referent rabbit fascia; see Fig. 3, where the individual material pairs are listed. The basic PDMS-
158 PDMS model described in [17] was used as the first model A. The second model B is composed
159 of PDMS-PDMS 10 ShA (acetoxo-PDMS, Elastosil® E43 Transparent, Wacker Chemie AG),
160 $R_a = 1.08 \mu\text{m}$ and 3000 kPa tensile strength, with interlayers of PU gel 75 Sh00 Phantom (BTG
161 Standard 75, Technogel®, Germany GmbH), $R_a = 211.2 \text{ nm}$ and $>800 \text{ kPa}$ tensile strength
162 mimicking the fascia layers on the muscle. Since the fascia tissue is a membrane on the muscle
163 or adipose tissue, this model approached the situation of the human body. Model B used a pin
164 with a linear contact with a 50 mm radius. The third model C consists of the PDMS 10 ShA pin
165 and the PU gel plate labeling Phantom (BTG S 130 AX, Technogel®, Germany GmbH) with
166 30 Sh00 stiffness, $R_a = 1.1 \mu\text{m}$ and 60-70 kPa tensile strength, which is much more compliant
167 than PDMS, so mimicking the muscle more faithfully. For this purpose, even the pin was
168 upgraded to a larger radius of 50 mm, preserving the linear contact. Model D returned to PDMS-

169 PDMS with interlayers, this time made up of hydrogel. The PVA hydrogel ($R_a = 793.42 \text{ nm}$)
 170 was chosen based on its hydrophilic surface properties. Model E was a reference model and the
 171 most real one from PDMS-PDMS and interlayers of rabbit fascia with $21 \pm 4 \text{ MPa}$ tensile
 172 strength. Mechanical properties were measured as part of our other study [29]. The surface
 173 roughness of the fascia could not be determined under our laboratory conditions. Compared to
 174 porcine, the rabbit has one big advantage because there is an extra muscle (musculus panniculus
 175 carnosus) under the layer of skin and adipose tissue. Thanks to this muscle, the fascia is not
 176 embedded in fat, as it is in humans and pigs, and can be removed without deterioration. PDMS
 177 plates for the pin and also for the plate were 3.5 mm thick, while Phantom was 8 mm thick.
 178 Interlayer materials were 0.75-1 mm thick.
 179

180

181

Fig. 3 Investigated tribological models of fascia.

182

183 *2.3. Lubricants*

184 The solutions of HA were used as lubricants as it is in a real fascia. It is a non-Newtonian
185 lubricant where the degree of polymerization results in differences in viscosity. This depends
186 on chemical properties such as molecular weight and concentration of the solution. In general,
187 increased molecular weight and concentration lead to increased lubricant viscosity. Four
188 different combinations were chosen to lubricate fascia, as shown in Tab. 1. A commercial
189 rheometer Discovery HR 30 (New Castle, DE, USA) was used in a cone-plate configuration at
190 37 °C for viscosity measurements. The experiments were carried out using a stainless-steel cone
191 and plate geometry (40 mm diameter with a 1° cone angle). The results are shown in Tab. 1 and
192 the rheological curves can be seen in **Appendix A**.

193

194

Tab. 1 List of lubricants used in the experimental study.

Designation	Molecular weight	Concentration	Viscosity (37 °C)
HA610a	610 kDa	20 mg/ml	1191.47 mPa.s
HA316a	316 kDa	20 mg/ml	202.94 mPa.s
HA101a	101 kDa	20 mg/ml	27.49 mPa.s
HA316b	316 kDa	10 mg/ml	59.72 mPa.s

195

196

197 The wettability of the materials has also been measured to check whether the surfaces are
198 hydrophobic or hydrophilic concerning the lubricants HA610a, HA316b and deionized water
199 as a reference. A small amount of lubricant (6 µl) was applied to the material surface, and the
200 contact angle was measured in 2D using a microscope (Fig. 4). Individual contact angles are
201 shown in Tab. 2.

202

203

204

205

Tab. 2 Contact angles between fluids and materials.

Lubricant	PDMS	PU gel 75	Phantom	PVA hydrogel	Fascia
HA610a	100.09°	52.03°	41.27°	45.31°	50.09°
HA316b	107.65°	63.05°	45.00°	31.02°	28.33°
Water - reference	82.63°	78.95°	41.20°	25.33°	39.28°

206

207

Fig. 4 Wettability of rubbing surfaces.

208

209 2.4. Statistical methods

210 The findings were shown as the average of 3 measurements along with their standard deviation
 211 (SD). The statistical analysis involved two-way ANOVA, followed by either Tukey's
 212 comparison tests. For each comparison, individual variances were calculated. In all cases,
 213 significance was determined as *P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001, and ****P < 0.0001.

214

215 3. Results

216 3.1. Effect of tribopair geometry

217 The effect of three different radii was investigated on two models: a model A (a commonly
 218 used model in biotribology to simulate compliant contacts) and a PDMS-Phantom model

219 (model C, the least stiff material of those used in this study). Each test condition was assessed
220 by focusing on dynamic friction. This involved selecting a subset of the stroke within a region
221 where the friction remains relatively stable, devoid of maximum peaks – where the static
222 friction occurred. More information can be found at Appendix A. Fig. 5(d-i) illustrates an
223 example of a set of strokes in both directions. The strokes within each curve were averaged to
224 represent friction curves shown in Fig. 5(b-c) and singular friction data points in the figure
225 presented in Fig. 5a. The COF was compared for each measurement where the pin radius
226 increased from 8.6 mm through 30 to 50 mm (Fig. 5(a-c)). Expanding the contact area through
227 an increase in pin radius, while maintaining the same applied normal load, results in a reduction
228 of contact pressure. In this particular phase of the experiment, both models were lubricated with
229 HA101a. The results revealed a significant correlation between COF and pin radius. In the
230 model A, increasing the contact area led to an overall friction reduction of 22% from R8.6 to
231 R50. However, COF between R30 and R50 remained unchanged. The friction curves remained
232 consistent throughout the duration of the test and showed the same shape and progression.
233 Similarly, in the model C, increasing the contact area led to an overall 36% reduction in friction,
234 but the drop between R30 and R50 was more evident. In this case, the friction curves fluctuated
235 compared to those observed in the model A. The fluctuation of the curves is closely related to
236 the friction force, shown in Fig. 5(d-i), and will be discussed in more detail in the discussion.
237

238

239 *Fig. 5 Influence of tribopair geometry on friction lubricated by HA101a. a) summary bar plot of COF, b) and c) development*
 240 *of friction in time, d) -i) individual friction force curves with velocity profile [30].*

241

242 3.2. Testing of friction in fascia models

243 The second step of the study involved the simultaneous development of the models alongside
 244 the first step. In this phase, model A from the preliminary study was also subjected to testing
 245 using HA316b and HA610a. Each test condition was evaluated with a focus on dynamic friction
 246 as in the test before - examples are shown in Fig. 6(b-k). The strokes within each curve were
 247 averaged to represent singular friction data points in Fig. 6a. The sliding friction coefficient was
 248 then compared between the developed versions, as illustrated in Fig. 6a. Firstly, model B with
 249 pin R50 and with an additional upper layer of PU gel with a hardness of 75 Sh00 was introduced

250 to simulate the fascia layer. Comparing it to the preliminary model A reported COF values of
251 0.050; SD = 0.005588 for HA316b and 0.115; SD = 0.005236 for HA610a, the COF decreased
252 for both HA316b to 0.045; SD = 0.002489 and HA610a to 0.058; SD = 0.004945. The friction
253 curves exhibited more consistent progress over the testing time and became more stable.
254 Secondly, model C utilized PU gel with a hardness of 30 Sh00 (Phantom) instead of PDMS as
255 the muscle, along with the R50 pin. Notably, the application of Phantom resulted in a
256 significantly higher level of friction testing for both lubricants, exceeding the others by an order
257 of magnitude. Next, model D reverted to PDMS as the muscle while retaining the R50 pin. The
258 fascia was represented by the use of PVA hydrogel. Model D reported COF values of 0.019;
259 SD = 0.000102 for HA316b and 0.034; SD = 0.001976 for HA610a, indicating a decrease in
260 friction compared to model B. Finally, the model E with rabbit fascia was developed, with the
261 base muscle layers composed of PDMS. The model utilized the largest designed contact area
262 of the tribopair using the R50 pin. Model E reported COF values of 0.029; SD = 0.000814 for
263 HA316b and 0.056; SD = 0.001553 for HA610a. As can be seen in Tab. 3. in comparison to
264 rabbit fascia model, models B and D exhibited the most similar friction properties for both
265 lubricants. The comparison between Model B and Model E showed a statistically significant
266 difference for HA316b (**; P = 0.0029), while for HA610a, the comparison did not exhibit
267 statistical significance (ns; P = 0.9823). When comparing Model D and Model E, the analysis
268 revealed that there was no statistically significant difference for HA316b (ns; P = 0.1168).
269 However, for HA610a, the comparison demonstrated a highly significant difference (****; P <
270 0.0001). The other models show a high level of significance for both lubricants compared to
271 model E.

272

273
274

Fig. 6 Friction of tribological fascia models. a) summary bar plot, b)-k) individual friction force curves with velocity profile [30].

275 As shown in Fig. 6(b-k), even models B, D, and E exhibited the fluctuations. The friction forces
 276 for HA610a were generally higher than those for HA316b, and the shape of the friction force
 277 curves was quite similar across the models for both lubricants. However, the friction force
 278 curves differed between the models themselves.

279

280

Tab. 3 Statistical analysis of tribological fascia models comparison.

Designation	HA316b		HA610a	
	Significance	Adjusted P value	Significance	Adjusted P value
"Model A vs. Model B"	ns	0.7082	****	<0.0001
"Model A vs. Model C"	****	<0.0001	****	<0.0001
"Model A vs. Model D"	****	<0.0001	****	<0.0001
"Model A vs. Model E"	***	0.0002	****	<0.0001
"Model B vs. Model C"	****	<0.0001	****	<0.0001
"Model B vs. Model D"	****	<0.0001	****	<0.0001
"Model B vs. Model E"	**	0.0029	ns	0.9823
"Model C vs. Model D"	****	<0.0001	****	<0.0001
"Model C vs. Model E"	****	<0.0001	****	<0.0001
"Model D vs. Model E"	ns	0.1168	****	<0.0001

281

282 *3.3. Friction tests of rabbit fascia – model E*

283 The third part of this study focused on investigating the influence of molecular weight and
 284 concentration of HA on the friction of the rabbit fascia model E. The pin and plate consisted of
 285 a PDMS base-muscle layer with a rabbit fascia layer on top. Four solutions (listed in Tab 1) of
 286 HA were utilized, varying in molecular weight from 101 to 610 kDa and concentrations of 10
 287 mg/ml and 20 mg/ml. The results indicated that the friction values were highest (0.056; SD =
 288 0.001552) when using HA610a with a concentration of 20 mg/ml ($\eta = 1191.47$ mPa.s), while

289 the lowest friction values (0.026; SD = 0.0008719) were observed with HA101a at the same
 290 concentration ($\eta = 27.4923$ mPa.s). Furthermore, HA316a at a concentration of 20 mg/ml ($\eta =$
 291 202.94 mPa.s) exhibited a higher COF (0.040; SD = 0.001574) compared to HA316b at 10
 292 mg/ml ($\eta = 59.72$ mPa.s), which resulted in a COF of 0.029; SD = 0.0008141. Therefore, as
 293 depicted in Fig. 7, friction increased with both increasing molecular weight and concentration
 294 of HA in the solution. The progression of friction over time is also illustrated in Fig. 7b. Friction
 295 curves for HA101 showed some fluctuation but otherwise consistent behavior over time. In
 296 contrast, for the other lubricants, the friction curves exhibited a slight increase over time.
 297

298
 299 *Fig. 7 Influence of concentration and molecular weight on the friction of rabbit fascia [30].*
 300

301 4. Discussion

302 4.1. Effect of tribopair geometry

303 In this section of the experiment, two models were employed: model A and model C. Model A
 304 was selected due to its widespread use in biotribological studies, specifically in areas like the
 305 eye-eyelid [11] or mouth [31]; [32]. Model C was chosen based on input from physiotherapists
 306 and their sensory experiences during manual therapy of the lower back. The redesign of the
 307 pin's shape and dimensions aimed to make it more closely resemble real fascia contact. The
 308 study's findings suggest that friction levels decrease as the contact area increase in both model
 309 A and model C contacts. These results align with previous studies [33; 34; 35] that established

310 a correlation between the increased COF and increased normal load respectively contact
311 pressure in compliant contact. The data in [34] indicates that, for both cylindrical and spherical
312 probes, the friction due to deformation rises as the normal load and sliding speed increase.
313 Moreover, this study indicates that in a lubricated condition, an increase in both speed and
314 normal load leads to a tendency for the balance between adhesion and deformation to approach
315 a 50/50 ratio. The split between the adhesive and deformation components is investigated by
316 two terms friction model [36; 37]. The first component - adhesive - relies on the mechanism the
317 energy that's lost when small connections break between two surfaces sliding against each
318 other. These connections happen because of short-range attractions between molecules, like the
319 ones in van der Waals interactions [36].

320

321 The role of adhesion in contributing significantly to the total friction of compliant contacts is
322 widely known [23; 38]. Hence, it is valuable to examine not only the COF curves but also the
323 frictional force curves themselves. These curves are notably influenced by the variable
324 geometry of the contact area, clearly showcasing the presence of adhesive behavior rather than
325 pure sliding indicating boundary lubrication regime. The tangential movements on the
326 elastomer surface which can be seen in Fig. 5, suggest that friction arises from the interplay
327 between adhesive dragging and an ongoing relaxation process at the microscale level. In model
328 A, the frictional force increased during the forward motion, with multiple small adhesion cycles
329 until peak occurred. An explanation is offered by Barquins [39], who describes that elastomer
330 molecules undergo thermal agitation at the interface, with their jump directions being random
331 in the absence of external stress. The application of a frictional force guides these jumps to
332 alleviate stress. During sliding, molecular bonds consistently detach from and reattach to the
333 slider, causing small jumps in the elastomer chain ends. The transitions from peak to valley
334 happened almost instantly, as a result of a change of direction into a movement of the opposite

335 sense. At this point, the pin velocity is zero, so the COF value corresponds to the static friction
336 value.

337

338 On the other hand, model C exhibited a rapid increase to the peak and a similarly quick decrease
339 during the sinusoidal cycle. Interestingly, while the adhesion pattern and shape were relatively
340 consistent in model A for both motion direction, except for an increase in the peak value not
341 used to calculate the COF, model C displayed unsymmetrical deformation phase at all holder
342 sizes. In positive stage of motion there is a steep increase of tangential force almost without
343 adhesion jumps. The dissipation of frictional force not only mirrors the strength of interfacial
344 bonds but also signifies the viscoelastic loss characteristics of the elastomer. In the other words,
345 the elastomer friction mechanism is a viscoelastic process [23; 39]. Nevertheless, the shift
346 towards the negative direction doesn't occur abruptly but rather follows an exponential pattern.
347 This suggests that the extensive deformation and accumulation of material in front of the pin
348 are substantial enough for the elastomer deformation to entirely take precedence. This
349 dominance arises from the material's high ductility and slow relaxation resulting in high
350 resistance to movement. Consequently, during the pin's movement in the opposite direction, we
351 observe the material attempting to relax, facilitated by the moving pin. As a result, the
352 deformation in the negative direction is considerably smaller, leading to an asymmetry in the
353 frictional force between both movement directions. So, this is a nice demonstration of the
354 hysteresis of the material [40]. As the contact changed to R30 and R50, the adhesion became
355 evident. Moreover, as the contact area increased, the peak value of the maximum friction force
356 decreased. This indicates that material stiffness plays a more significant role in influencing the
357 occurrence, origin and characterisation of adhesion and deformation in both model A and C,
358 rather than the contact area. This observation is supported by other relevant studies [41; 42].

359

360 In summary, these experiments highlighted the importance of pin shape, material properties,
361 and normal force in determining friction behavior in compliant contacts. The findings
362 emphasized the need for careful consideration of these factors to accurately simulate real
363 *in-vivo* contact conditions and optimize performance in mechanical systems.

364

365 *4.2. Testing of friction in fascia models*

366 The primary objective of this study was to develop a tribological model for fascia. While the
367 most sophisticated model would involve rabbit fascia, the scarcity and limited availability of
368 biological samples prompted the search for a suitable technical equivalent within elastomers.
369 In this regard, it is well-known that the sliding friction coefficient increases as the elastic
370 modulus of elastomers decreases [25]. This aligns with the understanding that a less stiff
371 material has the capacity to produce a greater resistive force when subjected to shearing –
372 therefore the friction force increases [43; 44]. Put simply, softer compounds exhibited higher
373 adhesion at the same velocities due to time-dependent viscoelasticity. Additionally, employing
374 a more viscous material in the tribopair resulted in more pronounced oscillations in the friction
375 force [45], as we can observe in Fig. 5(d-i) and Fig. 6(b-k). The observed increase in friction can
376 be attributed to the contribution of friction caused by adhesion and hysteresis losses occurring
377 in compliant contact [19; 23; 34]. This results in a significant difference in friction magnitude
378 between PDMS- and Phantom-based models, as elaborated earlier in the discussion. The control
379 of the adhesion primarily lies with the stiffness, as previously observed [43; 46]. Furthermore,
380 what's particularly intriguing is that the adhesion remains unaffected by the type or viscosity of
381 the lubricant used; rather, it is predominantly influenced by the materials in the tribopair [45].
382 However, in the boundary and mixed lubrication regimes, friction is significantly influenced by
383 material roughness, as asperities serve as lubricant reservoirs within the contact [20]. It's worth
384 noting that silicone-like elastomers, including those utilized in this study, generally exhibit
385 relatively high roughness due to the manufacturing process [47]. Specific roughness values are

386 given in Materials and methods. However, in study by Tiwari et al. [46] the impact of raised
387 roughness varied based on the stiffness of the elastomer compound. This distinct behavior can
388 be clarified by considering the extra elastic energy accumulated when stiffer elastomer makes
389 contact with a rough surface and the supplementary contact area observed in the case of more
390 compliant, softer elastomer. Which, in the case of a compliant elastomers, indicates the
391 contribution of hysteresis friction. Due to hysteresis friction being attributed to internal energy
392 dissipation related to elastomer deformation, the friction force rises with the increasing
393 deformation of elastomer asperities. Consequently, the hysteresis friction is likely to increase
394 with a higher Ra of the elastomer, resulting in an elevated friction coefficient [48]. However,
395 considering the generally low friction in all models except for model C, it can be inferred that
396 the adhesive component of friction decreases in the representation of the hysteretic component.

397

398 The hydrophilicity and hydrophobicity of the interface between the material and the lubricant
399 represent additional material properties that influence contact behavior [18]. All the materials
400 used to create the fascial model were measured with the two lubricants employed in the
401 tribological testing of the developed models. The data presented in Tab. 2 provide information
402 on these properties. Based on the data analysis, it is evident that the PDMS/PU gel and
403 PDMS/PVA hydrogel models exhibited friction values closest to the rabbit fascia model for
404 both lubricants. In terms of wettability, the PU gel exhibited a comparable contact angle to the
405 fascia for HA610a, indicating a similar COF. The same situation is repeated for hydrogel, rabbit
406 fascia and HA316b lubricant. Therefore, it can be assumed that this parameter influences the
407 friction results. A previous study [49] investigating the wettability of pure hydrogel reported
408 strong hydrophilicity when in contact with water, which may explain the similar COF measured
409 for the low viscous HA316b (the viscosity data can be seen in Tab. 1). Consequently, both
410 models (B and D) show promise as replacements for real fascia, with the PU gel being more

411 suitable for high viscous lubricants and the PVA hydrogel for low viscous lubricants. The
412 opposing trend of lubrication observed in the C model is likely attributed to the combination of
413 low rigid material, hydrophobicity, and substantial deformations. The effects of the lubricants
414 used will be discussed more in the next part of the discussion.

415

416 In conclusion, this study addressed the development of a tribological model for fascia by
417 considering alternative materials due to the limited availability of biological samples.
418 The results indicate that the choice of material properties, such as elastic modulus, roughness,
419 and wettability affects the friction behavior in compliant contact. The PDMS/PU gel (model B)
420 and PDMS/PVA hydrogel (model D) exhibited friction values closest to the rabbit fascia model
421 (model E) for the lubricants tested. These findings provide valuable insights for the selection
422 of suitable technical equivalents for fascia in future tribological studies.

423

424 *4.3. Friction tests of rabbit fascia*

425 The rabbit fascia model was utilized in this study to explore the impact of HA solution
426 properties on friction using a biological tissue. It is worth mentioning that HA is known for its
427 effect to reduce friction, for example between the eye and the eyelid or in the natural and
428 artificial joints [50; 11; 51; 52]. Together with other substances such as phospholipids or
429 proteins, HA can lubricate brilliantly even in boundary regime. However, friction-reducing
430 properties of HA are strongly depended on its properties such as molecular weight and
431 concentration. In general, molecular weight in the body varies. For example, in human
432 physiological synovial fluid, it typically ranges from 6000 to 7000 kDa but, in rheumatoid fluid,
433 the molecular weight is comparatively lower, falling within the range of 3000 to 5000 kDa [53;
434 54]. In addition, the estimated thickness of the HA fluid layer within the fascia is on the order
435 of tens of microns [55], which is significant compared to the size of the molecules and even the
436 roughness of the fascia [56]. Consequently, in cases where the concentration or molecular

437 weight of HA is high, the increased viscosity resulting from the resistance to flow can impact
438 lubrication [57; 58]. Indicating that full-film lubrication likely prevails within the closed fascial
439 system, it is quite sensible to explore how the specific properties of individual solutions
440 influence friction in the fascia.

441

442 The findings in the study indicated that an increase in the viscosity of HA in the solution
443 corresponded to an increase in the COF. The viscosity of an ideal polymer solution is
444 proportional to the fraction of the solution volume occupied by polymer chains. This occupied
445 volume fraction can also be expressed in terms of the mass concentration of the polymer
446 multiplied by the polymer specific volume [57]. In other words, viscosity is influenced by the
447 length and number of polymer chains in the solution, as well as the size of the molecules. As
448 the molecular weight and concentration increase, the presence of densely packed polymer
449 chains restricts the ability of the polymer to find space for movement within the solution.
450 Consequently, under conditions of low sliding motion and applied load, friction between the
451 molecules has the potential to increase. This is finally confirmed by the results of the experiment
452 carried out.

453

454 In our investigation of the developed fascial model, high molecular weight HA610a was
455 utilized. This lubricant exhibits a relatively high viscosity. As depicted in the results presented
456 in Fig. 7, it demonstrates increased friction when paired with the fascia compared to the lower
457 viscosity lubricants employed. It's important to remember that the primary objective of this
458 study was to create a tribological model for fascia, driven by the potential application of
459 identifying ideal HA properties for a medical viscosupplement designed to address low back
460 pain. Elevated HA production represents the body's initial response to enhance the smooth
461 interaction between two surfaces, similar to the mechanism observed in a synovial joint [10].

462 When HA is present within thin connective tissue layers, the HA chains can intertwine, thereby
463 contributing to the hydrodynamic properties of the solution [59]. Consequently, based on the
464 initial results, it appears impractical to exclusively concentrate on high viscosity, and therefore
465 high molecular weight, and/or highly concentrated HA solutions in future research.

466
467 *4.4. Limitations*

468 The authors acknowledge several potential limitations in the current study. The initial section
469 of the publication concentrates on assessing the impact of pin geometry using materials of
470 varying rigidity. This aspect of the experiment has been carried out using a single lubricant,
471 specifically designated as HA101a. The decision to utilize only one lubricant was influenced
472 by literature, such as Kim et al. [45], which suggests that the primary factor influencing
473 outcomes should be the material in the tribopair rather than the lubricant. Consequently, there
474 is a strong basis to presume that the friction trends observed for the specified material models
475 and pin geometry will persist when employing any other lubricant.

476
477 Further, in examining the five developed models, the choice of employing HA316b and
478 HA610a lubricants is justified as follows. HA610a was selected due to its high viscosity, being
479 the most viscous lubricant available for the study. The authors note in the current discussion
480 that in lubricated parts of the human body, such as joints, HA tends to have a higher molecular
481 weight. On the other hand, HA316b is among the less viscous lubricants used in the study,
482 containing half the concentration of HA compared to HA101a. This led to concerns about the
483 lower stability of the solution as a fascia lubricant, though this concern was ultimately not
484 substantiated. However, testing all five models with all four lubricants would have been
485 excessively time-consuming, prompting the authors to opt for the more streamlined approach
486 of using the two specified lubricants.

487

488 Other possible limitation of this study is that rabbit fascia was used as a representative tissue
489 for human fascia. Typically, porcine and bovine specimens are more frequently employed as
490 human models. However, in these animals, it remains unclear how to separate deep fascia from
491 fat without causing damage. This aspect suggests a major challenge for future research using
492 biological samples to investigate friction and lubrication of fascia.

493

494 **5. Conclusions**

495 The aim of this study was to develop a tribological model of the fascia through tribological
496 modelling and material substitution and to study the friction in these models. Four tribological
497 models of fascia were constructed from technical elastomers and one from rabbit fascia. This
498 paper was built upon the preliminary study [17] and presents the following findings:

- 499 • increased contact area resulting in improved pressure distribution and decreased friction
500 for both the basic and the most compliant model. With the more compliant model, the
501 change in geometry had a significantly more positive effect,
- 502 • PVA hydrogel and PU gel (stiffness of 75 Sh00) tribopair was identified as potential
503 replacements for real biological samples based on comparing four different tribological
504 models,
- 505 • concerning high-viscosity HA lubricant, PU gel is more suitable replacement of fascia,
506 while PVA is recommended when focusing on low-viscosity lubricants,
- 507 • a strong correlation between friction and HA solution's molecular weight and
508 concentration was found based on investigating rabbit fascia model.

509 The findings and models from the study will be further used for a follow-up study to define the
510 properties leading to low friction in the fascia and will serve as a basis for the development of
511 a viscosupplement for the treatment of lower back pain.

512

513 **Acknowledgment**

514 This publication was supported by the project "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-
515 inspired Systems", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme
516 Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

517

518 This project (Fascia lubrication and regeneration by hyaluronan) has received funding from the
519 Operational Programme Enterprise and Innovations for Competitiveness 2014-2020 (OPEIC)
520 under agreement No CZ.01.1.02/0.0/0.0/19_262/0020005.

521

522 **Declaration of interests**

523 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
524 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

525

526 **Ethical approval**

527 Ethical review and approval were waived for this study due to the sole use of animal cadavers
528 for tissue harvesting. The use of tissue from animal cadavers was in accordance with relevant
529 guidelines and regulations in Czech Republic. The procedure for obtaining the thoracolumbar
530 fascia was approved by the Ethics Committee of the MINISTRY OF EDUCATION, YOUTH
531 AND PHYSICAL EDUCATION ID: MSMT- 2036/2022-3. Human Ethics and Consent to
532 Participate declarations: not applicable.

533

534 **Data Availability**

535 Experimental data for Understanding frictional behavior in fascia tissues through tribological
536 modeling and material substitution available at resource

537 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10513262>. Also documented in the manuscript as source
538 number [30].

539

540 **References**

- [1] S.Chen, M.Chen, X.Wu, S.Lin, C.Tao, H.Cao, Z.Shao, G.Xiao, Global, regional and national burden of low back pain 1990–2019: A systematic analysis of the Global Burden of Disease study 2019, *Journal of Orthopaedic Translation*. vol. 32 (2022) 49-58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jot.2021.07.005>.
- [2] F.Balagué, A.Mannion, F.Pellisé, C.Cedraschi, Non-specific low back pain, *The Lancet*. vol. 379 (2012) 482-491. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(11\)60610-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(11)60610-7).
- [3] C.Chen, A.Nizar, Myofascial Pain Syndrome in Chronic Back Pain Patients, *The Korean Journal of Pain*. vol. 24 (2011) 100-104. <https://doi.org/10.3344/kjp.2011.24.2.100>.
- [4] J.Tesarz, U.Hoheisel, B.Wiedenhöfer, S.Mense, Sensory innervation of the thoracolumbar fascia in rats and humans, *Neuroscience*. vol. 194 (2011) 302-308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2011.07.066>.
- [5] H.Langevin, J.Fox, C.Koptiuch, G.Badger, A.Greenan- Naumann, N.Bouffard, E.Konofagou, W.Lee, J.Triano, S.Henry, Reduced thoracolumbar fascia shear strain in human chronic low back pain, *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*. vol. 12 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2474-12-203>.
- [6] C.Stecco, V.Macchi, A.Porzionato, F.Duparc, R.De Caro, The fascia: The forgotten structure, *Journal of anatomy and Embryology*. vol. 116 (3) (2011) 127-138. <https://doi.org/10.13128/IJAE-10683>.
- [7] M.Blasi, J.Blasi, T.Domingo, A.Pérez-Bellmunt, M.Miguel-Pérez, Anatomical and histological study of human deep fasciae development, *Surgical and Radiologic Anatomy*. vol. 37 (2015) 571-578. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00276-014-1396-1>.
- [8] C.Stecco, R.Stern, A.Porzionato, V.Macchi, S.Masiero, A.Stecco, R.De Caro, Hyaluronan within fascia in the etiology of myofascial pain, *Surgical and Radiologic Anatomy*. vol. 33 (2011) 891-896. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00276-011-0876-9>.
- [9] P.Pavan, A.Stecco, R.Stern, P.logna Prat, C.Stecco, Fibrosis and densification: Anatomical vs functional alteration of the fascia, *Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies*. vol. 20 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbmt.2015.07.029>.
- [10] P.Pavan, A.Stecco, R.Stern, C.Stecco, Painful Connections: Densification Versus Fibrosis of Fascia, *Current Pain and Headache Reports*. vol. 18 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11916-014-0441-4>.
- [11] M.Černohlávek, M.Brandejsová, P.Štěpán, H.Vagnerová, M.Hermannová, K.Kopecká, J.Kulhánek, D.Nečas, M.Vrbka, V.Velebný, G.Huerta-Angeles, Insight into the Lubrication and

- Adhesion Properties of Hyaluronan for Ocular Drug Delivery, *Biomolecules*. vol. 11 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/biom11101431>.
- [12] S.Derler, U.Schrade, L.Gerhardt, Tribology of human skin and mechanical skin equivalents in contact with textiles, *Wear*. vol. 263 (2007) 1112-1116.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wear.2006.11.031>.
- [13] A.Dąbrowska, G.Rotaru, F.Spano, C.Affolter, G.Fortunato, S.Lehmann, S.Derler, N.Spencer, R.Rossi, A water-responsive, gelatine-based human skin model, *Tribology International*. vol. 113 (2017) 316-322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2017.01.027>.
- [14] A.Watrelet, T.Kuhl, A.Waterhouse, Friction forces of saliva and red wine on hydrophobic and hydrophilic surfaces, *Food Research International*. vol. 116 (2019) 1041-1046.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2018.09.043>.
- [15] R.Edmonds, T.Finney, M.Bull, A.Watrelet, T.Kuhl, Friction measurements of model saliva-wine solutions between polydimethylsiloxane surfaces, *Food Hydrocolloids*. vol. 113 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2020.106522>.
- [16] D.DRESSELHUIS, E.DEHOOG, M.COHENSTUART, G.VANAKEN, Application of oral tissue in tribological measurements in an emulsion perception context, *Food Hydrocolloids*. vol. 22 (2008) 323-335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2006.12.008>.
- [17] A.Streďanská, D.Nečas, M.Vrbka, I.Křupka, M.Hartl, E.Toropitsyn, J.Husby, Development of Tribological Model of Human Fascia: The Influence of Material Hardness and Motion Speed, *Biotribology*. vol. 30 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotri.2022.100209>.
- [18] J.Bongaerts, K.Fourtouni, J.Stokes, Soft-tribology: Lubrication in a compliant PDMS–PDMS contact, *Tribology International*. vol. 40 (2007) 1531-1542.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2007.01.007>.
- [19] P.Sadowski, S.Stupkiewicz, Friction in lubricated soft-on-hard, hard-on-soft and soft-on-soft sliding contacts, *Tribology International*. vol. 129 (2019) 246-256.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2018.08.025>.
- [20] N.Selway, V.Chan, J.Stokes, Influence of fluid viscosity and wetting on multiscale viscoelastic lubrication in soft tribological contacts, *Soft Matter*. vol. 13 (2017) 1702-1715.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C6SM02417C>.
- [21] M.Schneemilch, N.Quirke, Effect of oxidation on the wettability of poly(dimethylsiloxane) surfaces, *The Journal of Chemical Physics*. vol. 127 (2007).
<https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2770723>.
- [22] H.Hillborg, M.Sandelin, U.Gedde, Hydrophobic recovery of polydimethylsiloxane after exposure to partial discharges as a function of crosslink density, *Polymer*. vol. 42 (2001) 7349-7362. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-3861\(01\)00202-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-3861(01)00202-6).
- [23] A.Schallamach, How does rubber slide?, *Wear*. vol. 17 (1971) 301-312.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1648\(71\)90033-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1648(71)90033-0).

- [24] J.de Vicente, J.Stokes, H.Spikes, Rolling and sliding friction in compliant, lubricated contact, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part J: Journal of Engineering Tribology*. vol. 220 (2006) 55-63. <https://doi.org/10.1243/13506501JET90>.
- [25] C.Myant, H.Spikes, J.Stokes, Influence of load and elastic properties on the rolling and sliding friction of lubricated compliant contacts, *Tribology International*. vol. 43 (2010) 55-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2009.04.034>.
- [26] Y.Xu, B.Cartwright, L.Advincula, C.Myant, J.Stokes, Generalised scaling law for soft contact tribology: Influence of load and asymmetric surface deformation, *Tribology International*. vol. 163 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2021.107192>.
- [27] W.Albert, C.Duncan, N.Currie-Jackson, V.Gaudet, J.Callaghan, Biomechanical assessment of massage therapists, *Occupational Ergonomics*. vol. 6 (2006) 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.3233/OER-2006-6101>.
- [28] G.Plasqui, A.Bonomi, K.Westerterp, Daily physical activity assessment with accelerometers: new insights and validation studies, *Obesity Reviews*. vol. 14 (2013) 451-462. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.12021>.
- [29] K.Nešporová, J.Matonohová, J.Husby, E.Toropitsyn, L.Stupecká, A.Husby, T.Suchánková Kleplová, A.Středanská, M.Šimek, D.Nečas, M.Vrbka, R.Schleip, V.Velebný, Injecting hyaluronan in the thoracolumbar fascia: A model study, *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. vol. 253 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.126879>.
- [30] Experimental data for Understanding frictional behavior in fascia tissues through tribological modeling and material substitution, in: *Zenodo*, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10513262>.
- [31] J.Vinke, H.Kaper, A.Vissink, P.Sharma, An ex vivo salivary lubrication system to mimic xerostomic conditions and to predict the lubricating properties of xerostomia relieving agents, *Scientific Reports*. vol. 8 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-27380-7>.
- [32] S.Vlădescu, M.Agurto, C.Myant, M.Boehm, S.Baier, G.Yakubov, G.Carpenter, T.Reddyhoff, Protein-induced delubrication: How plant-based and dairy proteins affect mouthfeel, *Food Hydrocolloids*. vol. 134 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2022.107975>.
- [33] A.Rennie, P.Dickrell, W.Sawyer, Friction coefficient of soft contact lenses: measurements and modeling, *Tribology Letters*. vol. 18 (2005) 499-504. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11249-005-3610-0>.
- [34] D.Mahdi, A.Riches, M.Gester, J.Yeomans, P.Smith, Rolling and sliding: Separation of adhesion and deformation friction and their relative contribution to total friction, *Tribology International*. vol. 89 (2015) 128-134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2014.12.021>.
- [35] C.Rand, A.Crosby, Friction of soft elastomeric wrinkled surfaces, *Journal of Applied Physics*. vol. 106 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3226074>.
- [36] M.Adams, B.Briscoe, S.Johnson, Friction and lubrication of human skin, *Tribology Letters*. vol. 26 (2007) 239-253. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11249-007-9206-0>.

- [37] J.van Kuilenburg, M.Masen, E.van der Heide, A review of fingerpad contact mechanics and friction and how this affects tactile perception, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part J: Journal of Engineering Tribology*. vol. 229 (2015) 243-258. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350650113504908>.
- [38] A.Schallamach, Friction and abrasion of rubber, *Wear*. vol. 1 (1958) 384-417. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1648\(58\)90113-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1648(58)90113-3).
- [39] M.Barquins, Adherence, friction and wear of rubber-like materials, *Wear*. vol. 158 (1992) 87-117. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1648\(92\)90033-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1648(92)90033-5).
- [40] V.Popov, *Contact Mechanics and Friction*, (2010) 362. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-10803-7>.
- [41] Y.Berdichevsky, J.Khandurina, A.Guttman, Y.Lo, UV/ozone modification of poly(dimethylsiloxane) microfluidic channels, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*. vol. 97 (2004) 402-408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2003.09.022>.
- [42] L.Xue, J.Pham, J.Iturri, A.del Campo, Stick–Slip Friction of PDMS Surfaces for Bioinspired Adhesives, *Langmuir*. vol. 32 (2016) 2428-2435. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.6b00513>.
- [43] A.Adam, D.Paulkowski, B.Mayer, Friction and Deformation Behavior of Elastomers, *Materials Sciences and Applications*. vol. 10 (2019) 527-542. <https://doi.org/10.4236/msa.2019.108038>.
- [44] L.Voll, V.Popov, Experimental investigation of the adhesive contact of an elastomer, *Physical Mesomechanics*. vol. 17 (2014) 232-235. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1029959914030096>.
- [45] A.Kim, A.Cholewinski, S.Mitra, B.Zhao, Viscoelastic tribopairs in dry and lubricated sliding friction, *Soft Matter*. vol. 16 (2020) 7447-7457. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0SM00516A>.
- [46] A.Tiwari, L.Dorogin, A.Bennett, K.Schulze, W.Sawyer, M.Tahir, G.Heinrich, B.Persson, The effect of surface roughness and viscoelasticity on rubber adhesion, *Soft Matter*. vol. 13 (2017) 3602-3621. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7SM00177K>.
- [47] X.Ye, H.Liu, Y.Ding, H.Li, B.Lu, Research on the cast molding process for high quality PDMS molds, *Microelectronic Engineering*. vol. 86 (2009) 310-313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mee.2008.10.011>.
- [48] T.Ido, T.Yamaguchi, K.Shibata, K.Matsuki, K.Yumii, K.Hokkirigawa, Sliding friction characteristics of styrene butadiene rubbers with varied surface roughness under water lubrication, *Tribology International*. vol. 133 (2019) 230-235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2019.01.015>.
- [49] T.Zhao, G.Wang, D.Hao, L.Chen, K.Liu, M.Liu, Macroscopic Layered Organogel-Hydrogel Hybrids with Controllable Wetting and Swelling Performance, *Advanced Functional Materials*. vol. 28 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201800793>.
- [50] D.Rebenda, M.Vrbka, D.Nečas, E.Toropitsyn, S.Yarimitsu, P.Čípek, M.Pravda, M.Hartl, Rheological and frictional analysis of viscosupplements towards improved lubrication of

human joints, *Tribology International*. vol. 160 (2021).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2021.107030>.

- [51] D.Nečas, V.Kulíšek, P.Štěpán, F.Ondraš, P.Čípek, G.Huerta-Angeles, M.Vrbka, Friction and Lubrication of Eye/Lens/Lid Interface: The Effect of Lubricant and Contact Lens Material, *Tribology Letters*. vol. 71 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11249-023-01787-4>.
- [52] D.Nečas, K.Sadecká, M.Vrbka, J.Gallo, A.Galandáková, I.Křupka, M.Hartl, Observation of lubrication mechanisms in knee replacement: A pilot study, *Biotribology*. vol. 17 (2019) 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotri.2019.02.001>.
- [53] J.Fraser, T.Laurent, U.Laurent, Hyaluronan: its nature, distribution, functions and turnover, *Journal of Internal Medicine*. vol. 242 (1997) 27-33. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2796.1997.00170.x>.
- [54] T.LAURENT, U.LAURENT, J.FRASER, The structure and function of hyaluronan: An overview, *Immunology and Cell Biology*. vol. 74 (1996) a1-a7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/icb.1996.32>.
- [55] C.Fede, A.Angelini, R.Stern, V.Macchi, A.Porzionato, P.Ruggieri, R.De Caro, C.Stecco, Quantification of hyaluronan in human fasciae: variations with function and anatomical site, *Journal of Anatomy*. vol. 233 (2018) 552-556. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joa.12866>.
- [56] S.Choi, J.Shin, Y.Cheong, H.Lee, K.Jin, H.Park, Nanostructural investigation of frontalis sling biomaterial surfaces, *Scanning*. vol. 33 (2011) 419-425. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sca.20233>.
- [57] M.Cowman, T.Schmidt, P.Raghavan, A.Stecco, Viscoelastic Properties of Hyaluronan in Physiological Conditions, *F1000Research*. vol. 4 (2015) 6-22. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.6885.1>.
- [58] S.Falcone, D.Palmeri, R.Berg, Rheological and cohesive properties of hyaluronic acid, *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research Part A*. 76A (2006) 721-728. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.30623>.
- [59] P.Matteini, L.Dei, E.Carretti, N.Volpi, A.Goti, R.Pini, Structural Behavior of Highly Concentrated Hyaluronan, *Biomacromolecules*. vol. 10 (2009) 1516-1522. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bm900108z>.

541

542 **Appendix A**

543 *The rheological properties of HA solutions*

544 Due to the non-Newtonian behavior of HA solutions, we not only provide the viscosity value
545 at zero shear rate but also publish viscosity curves within the shear gradient range of
546 1-1000 1/s. The zero-shear rate viscosity of HA solutions was determined using the Careau-
547 Yasuda model through TRIOS software.

548

549

550

Fig. 8 The rheological curves - HA solutions.

551

552 Data analysis

553 In order to separate dynamic friction from static friction, a post-process analysis using Matlab
554 software is performed after the data has been measured.

555

556

Fig. 9 Post-process data analysis example on Model B and C lubricated by HA316b.

557

558 Matlab function – *sgolayfilt*: translates the raw COF curve by a third-degree polynomial and
559 thus filters out static friction. The result is a blue filter COF curve.

560

561

Tab. 4 The comparison of raw and filtered mean COF values.

562

	Model B	Model C
Raw mean COF (-)	0.045758863	0.233958
Filtered mean COF (-)	0.045739873	0.243161
